

Figure 4

a

b

	Group-specific AA																	C-terminus consensus						
	27	215	216	238	239	243	275	295	300	303	307	311	316	336	341	346	349		350	351	352	371	379	385
Tub2A	N.A.	S	S	P	S	V	T	S	E	A	P	V	S	M	L	I	H	M	H	Q	T	Q	S	N.A.
Tub2C	A	N	T	T	T	G	V	A/S	S/I	N	Non-P	T/S	S	I	M	V	C/N	M	L	N/K	V/I	R	A	EXXPETXX
Tub2D3	A	N	T	T	T	G	V	S	Q	A	P	Q	A	I	M	V	Q	L	L	N	T	R	A	EGEGGAEAA
Tub2D4-Het	A	N	T	T	N	G	V/T	A	X	X	X	X	A	I	M	V	Q/N	M	L/I	X	T	R	A/S	N.A.
Tub2D4-Eu	V	N	T	T	T	G	V	A	G/Q	A	A	T/A	S	I	M	V	Q	M	L	N/Q	T	R	A	GEQEXAXQEAA
Tub2D2-Apo	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	V	A	S	N	P	Q	S	I	M	V	Q	M	L	S	T	R	G	XEXXEXEXX
Tub2D2-Eu	A	N	T	T/S	T/N	G	V	A	Q/S/T	A/S	S/P	Q/H	S/A	I	M	V	Q/N	M	L/F/M	X	T	R	G	EXXPETEGAX